

ENSURING CHEMICAL SAFETY OF BAKERY PRODUCTS IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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ABSTRACT

This article presents the results confirming the toxicity and chemical safety of the toxic elements of flour, dough and bread produced for “Obi non” enterprises: protein, amino acids, fractional structure of monocarbonyl compounds, their fatty acids, mineral content.

Keywords: chemicals, pathological state of toxicological poisoning

INTRODUCTION

Currently, due to the changing ecological situation in the country, the unfavorable weather conditions, uneven operation of industrial enterprises, especially the use of chemicals in agriculture and others (pollution, increased waste, weak control), a certain amount of various elements in the composition of food. falling can reduce its level of security.

In this regard, the President's address to the Oliy Majlis and many other resolutions and decrees set tasks on measures to further ensure food security of the country [1,2].

Since bread from food is a bakery product that a person consumes on a daily basis, in addition to its production being considered of great importance in the national economy. It is great importance to ensure its safety for the human body in consumption.

At present, 18-20% of the total industrial production in Uzbekistan is food production, the bulk of which falls on bakery products, and on average it reaches 920 thousand tons per year, which is especially important in preventing toxicological poisoning. ensuring food safety remains one of the most important tasks.

Timely low or high nutritional value of food, the presence of factors that alter the pathological state of the human body with various poisonings, and especially the presence of toxic elements, as well as its impact on the human body are among the current scientific research.

Therefore, the purpose of our scientific work is to conduct scientific research and

monitor the chemical safety of bakery products in the conditions of the Covid-19 pandemic, without violating the range and technology of bakery products, which are necessary for the human body.

The main part. Along with the rest of the world, Uzbekistan also produces a variety of bakery products, while in foreign countries the average per capita production of bread is 128 kg on an industrial scale, in Uzbekistan it is now 50-60 kg (including home bread - 19.8 kg), and the rest is different. made in small workshops, ovens and at home.

The range of bakery products differs mainly in the chemical composition and energy value of the technology of preparation from which they are made.

Analytical analysis of the literature on the range of bakery products, production technology and requirements to them showed that among other bread and bakery products produced in Uzbekistan is the so-called "Uzbek bread" and widely consumed "Obi-non". Therefore, we chose Obi-non as the object of study.

Republic of Uzbekistan (01 38-03) "Norms of sanitary safety of food raw materials were approved by the decision of the Chief State Sanitary Doctor of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 12, 2003 No. №7. According to this decision, the sanitary sanitary norms and nutritional value of bread and flour products are shown in Table 1.

The nutritional value of sanitary norms of safety of bread and flour products is determined by its: nutritional value of bread products (protein, fat, carbohydrates and total energy value); vitamins (thiamine-B₁, riboflavin-B₂, nicotine-RR); toxic elements (lead, arsenic, cadmium, mercury, copper, zinc), which are safety criteria; mycotoxins (afletoxin, desoxin and tenol, zearamenin, T-2 toxin); radionuclides (cesium-137, strontium-90); microbiological risk (BGKP-camforli, S-aureos, pathogenic; salmonella, mold) and others (Table 1).

1 - table

Sanitary norms and nutritional value of bread and flour products (0138-03 "Sanitary safety standards for food and raw materials)

№	Criteria of indicators	Unit of measurement	In 100 g of product	2003 №7.12.08 Resolution of the Chief State Sanitary Doctor of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
Nutritional value of bakery products:				
1	Protein	gr	8.0-13.0	
2	Oil	gr	1.0-8.0	
3	Carbohydrates	gr	45-55	
4	Energy value	K kal	210-340	
5	Iron	mg	1.8-3.0	
Vitamins:				
1	Thiamine (B ₁)	mg	0.15-0.4	
2	Riboflavin (B ₂)	mg	0.1-0.5	
3	Nicotine (PP)	mg	1.5-3.0	
Safety criterion				
Toxic elements				
1	Lead	mg / kg	0.5 0.35	Flour-grain products Bread products
2	Arsenic	mg / kg	0.2 0.15	Flour-grain products Bread products
3	Cadmium	mg / kg	0.1 0.07	Flour-grain products Bread products
4	Mercury	mg / kg	0.03	Flour-grain products Bread products
5	Copper	mg / kg	0.015	Flour-grain products Bread products
6	Zinc (zinc)	mg / kg	10 50	Flour-grain products Bread products
Mycotoxins				
1	AflotoxinB ₁		0.00015	Impossible
2	Desoxin and tenol		0.05	Impossible
3	Zearalenon		0.005	Impossible
4	T-2 toxin		0.05	Impossible
Radionucleoids				
1	Cesium – 137		40	Bk / kg
2	Strontium - 90		20	Bk / kg
Microbiological				
1	BGKP (coliform)	gr	1.0	
2	Saleros	gr	1.0	
3	Pathogenic salmonella	gr	25	
4	Mold fungus paper / g	SME gr	50	

In our study, we conducted a study of the dough and bread used to make «Obi-non», including its composition and the amount of toxic elements that are safety criteria.

Laboratory research was carried out mainly at the Samarkand SEC, the testing laboratory of the Samarkand Department of Standardization, Metrology and Certification and the laboratories of the Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service.

Methodology. The chemical composition of bread dough and raw materials was determined using the following general (colorimeter, chromatography, polarimetry, etc.) methods [3].

The amount of dry matter was determined by drying in a cabinet SESh-1 until it has a constant mass. Flour at a temperature of 105 ° C, dough and bread at 130° C in accordance with GOST 21094-75. The difference between the weights of the initial raw mass and the dry matter obtained was taken as the moisture content.

The active acidity of the bread dough was determined in RN-meters. The total acidity of flour in bread dough Chijov V.N. method and etc., titrated in 0.1 n alkaline solution according to GOST 5670-51 and called it Neumann degrees (N). The amount of crude gluten was determined in accordance with GOST 9404-60 by washing the dough in water (2H).

The total amount of lipids in the product was determined by extraction of the pulverized product according to the modified method of foil. In this case, a mixture of chloroform and ethanol in a ratio of 2: 1 was used in accordance with GOST 5668-68.

The results. Chromatograms of cadmium, lead, zinc and copper, which are toxic elements, were obtained from the Samarkand branch of “Asia-Afrosiyob”. The chromatogram graph showed that the flour examined contained only copper, no spirit, no lead.

The amount of copper in 1 kg is 2.18 mg. This amount is harmless and even beneficial when eating with normal bread, as a person’s daily copper intake is 0.5 mg per kg body weight.

It is known that different types of flour are produced and used for bakery products. In order to expand the object of research, we obtained a chromatogram of wheat flour of the 1st grade LLP "Zopolya" GPM Realty LLC in Tashkent (Chekhova Street), which showed that it did not contain cadmium, lead, zinc, or even copper, ie their flour content confirmed the absence of.

For the same purpose, a sample of bread produced at the Samarkand bakery proved to contain only copper, cadmium, lead and spirit elements. The detected copper

content in the sample was 0.32 mg / kg. It is harmless to the human body and satisfies its daily need for copper.

Samarkand city in the bakery "Registan", Samarkand region, Ishtikhon district, Suleymanov V. Cadmium, lead, copper and spirit elements were not detected in the bread made by "Oila-non". Therefore, their consumption is safe for the human body.

In addition to the above-mentioned metallic toxins, the chemical hazards of bread dough and bakery products were studied by their fractional structure: amino acids in protein, monocarbonyl compounds, fatty acids in them, the results of experimental studies are given in Tables 2 - 5.

Table 2

The amino acids (% in relation to proteins) in the protein content of grade 1 wheat flour and the dimensions that characterize these aminoacids

№	Name of aminoacids	1st grade flour [4]	Uzbek national bread	RK α -COOH	RK α -NH	RK gr-R
1	Leucine	6.15-0.08	6.23-0.03	2.30	8.2	
2	Valine	3.42-0.08	3.04-0.07			
3	Meanin	3.42-0.08	3.23-0.03	2.10	7.65	9.03
4	Asparagine acid	2.16-0.07	1.9-0.08	2.05	8.30	3.67
5	Serin	3.08-0.07	3.80-0.04	2.11	8.05	
6	Glutamic acid	28.05-0.07	25.98-0.03	2.09	8.87	4.11
7	Prolin	33.23-0.05	42.07	0.09		
8	Arginine	8.21-0.07	956-0.03	2.12	8.4	12.06

From the data in the table, it was found that 8 out of 19 amino acids were controlled in the protein of "Obi-non" made from 1st grade wheat flour, as their relative abundance ensures the safety of bread products. Type 1 wheat flour contains proline -33.23%, glutamic acid-28.05% and leucine -6.15%, which are considered to be the most essential for the human body, and amino acids are more than others. At the same time all aspartic acid -n -2.16%, serine -3.08% occur in relatively small amounts. In "Obi-non", which is made from this wheat flour, all of these amino acids are relatively low, but all of them are preserved. In general, the amino acid content of wheat protein is satisfactory, and its consumption ensures the safety of the human body. The results of the study of the fractional structure of monocarbonate compounds determined experimentally in the composition of wheat flour dough and "Obi- non" obtained for the study are presented in Table 3.

Table 3
Monocarbonate compounds of dough and bread
fractional structure.

№	Monocarboxy compounds	Composition of monocarboxy compounds (% of total amount)	
		The Uzbek national bread “Obi-non	
		In the dough	In the bread
1	Methyl glyoxal	4.01	3.46
2	Acetaldehyde	11.33	19.88
3	Acetone-n butanol	42.79	47.41
4	Izo oily aldehyde	19.14	10.06
5	2-methyl butanol	13.76	4.56
6	Isovalerian aldehyde	1.09	1.84
7	Methyl ethyl ketone	0.34	1.32
8	Not identified	0.34	0.87
9	Pentanon-2	0.14	0.52
10	Metimeropilketon	0.04	0.81
11	Hexanal	0.88	2.19
12	Butyl methyl ketone	0.09	2.12

It is known from the table that monocarbonate compounds with 12 names were detected in all dough and bakery products.

Some of them multiply when bread is made from dough. For example, acetaldehyde to 40%, acetone-n butanol to 1.5 isovalerian aldehyde to 60%, methyl ethyl ketone to 80%, and so on. Similarly, methylglyoxal, an isomole aldehyde, 2-methylbutanol, is sharply reduced. Such a change in them, i.e. a change in the dough to bread or bread types, also ensures the safety of the human body by maintaining the content of monocarbonate compounds.

In order to determine the lipids of bread products, the lipid fatty acid content of 1st grade wheat flour was determined. The results are given in Table 4.

Table 4
Fatty acid content of 1st grade wheat flour and bread lipids (in% of the total amount)

№	Names of fatty acids	1 variety of wheat flour[4]	The Uzbek national bread “Obi-non”
1	Palmitin	19.7+0.03	19.24+0.07
2	Stearin	1.6+0.06	1.56+0.06
3	Olein	15.7+0.05	13.20+0.03
4	Linol	57.7+0.08	60.05+0.05
5	Linolen	5.3+0.02	4.81+0.02
6	Amount of acids:		
	Saturated	21.3+0.04	21.30+0.07
	Unsaturated	78.7+0.05	78.70+0.05

The table shows that the content of saturated fatty acids in bread is 3.69 times higher than in unsaturated fatty acids, the ratio is the same as in the 1st grade, as well as the Uzbek national bread "Obi- non". From it, after preparing the dough, the amount of some fatty acids changes during the baking process. For example, palmitic, oleic (15.7 to 13.2) decreased, while linoleic acid increased (57.7 to 60.05). In general, all fatty acids are retained.

Table 5 shows the mineral content (mg / 100 g) of 1st grade wheat flour and Uzbek national bread “Obi-non” determined by express methods.

Table 5
Mineral composition of Uzbek bread
(mg / 100 g per product)

№	Minerals	1 variety of wheat flour	The Uzbek national bread “Obi-non”
1	P	121.08-0.03	141.34-0.05
2	K	227.14-0.05	268.87-0.03
3	Ca	49.93-0.04	69.59-0.06
4	Mg	1.09-0.08	1.20-0.05
5	Fe	2.19-0.06	2.43-0.06
6	Cu	0.41-0.04	0.39-0.05
7	Zn	1.72-0.02	1.83-0.04

The results given in the table show that it contains seven basic mineral elements. They contain the largest amount of K and Ca, which are the most important for the human body. The presence of water and Zn is also provided in sufficient quantities in the body. Of course, the presence of these in normal amounts in bread products ensures food safety in human life.

Conclusion

The following conclusions can be made on ensuring the chemical safety of bakery products in the conditions of the pandemic of Covid-19 bakery enterprises in Samarkand:

1. Control studies on cadmium, lead, zinc and copper, which are toxic elements in flour produced for “Obi-non” showed that they contain only copper, no spirit, no lead, and there is no risk of consumption.
2. “Obi-non” dough and bread: amino acids in protein, fractional structure of monocarbonyl compounds, their fatty acids, mineral content, edible and chemical safety.

References:

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